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CLASS CONTROL SKILLS ADOPTED BY TEACHERS FOR ENHANCING QUALITY TEACHING AND LEARNING IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study ascertained class control skills possessed by teachers for enhancing quality teaching and learning in public secondary schools in Anambra State. To this end, the study was guided by one research question and one null hypothesis tested at a 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 6,350 teachers in the 257 State-owned secondary schools in the State. A sample of 672 teachers was drawn using a multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected using a questionnaire titled "Teachers' Class Control Skills Questionnaire" (TCCSQ). The questionnaire was validated by three experts two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation. An internal consistency reliability index of 0.79 was obtained for the instrument using Cronbach's Alpha method. Data analysis was done using mean and t-test. The findings revealed that teachers adopted four of the six listed classroom control skills for quality teaching and learning. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on their class control skills for quality teaching and learning in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the researchers recommended that training programs in the form of workshops and seminars be organised by the State government regularly to refresh and sharpen teachers' class control skills in order to achieve quality education in the State.

KEYWORDS

Class control, skill, quality Teaching and learning.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the bedrock for any meaningful and sustainable development of any nation. It is a tool through which a country's socio-economic, scientific and technological development is achieved. It is also an opportunity through which both individual, group or any nation is economically, socially, culturally and technologically empowered. Education is the instrument for empowering young people with knowledge and skills which provide them access to productive employment. Education provides individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary to advance themselves and their nation socially, economically and politically.

The acquisition of knowledge and skills take place mainly in a classroom environment. Ogbonnaya (2013) explained that the classroom is responsible for holding students together by affording them the opportunity to interact with one another and through this interaction, grow physically, intellectually, and emotionally. This shows that a classroom is the power house where the success of teaching and learning process is generated, implemented and sustained. The classroom is an important place in the operation of any school because it holds the students together and offers them the opportunity of achieving the purpose of education. This could be why teachers' ability to manage classroom effectively has increasingly become a fundamental need in the quest for effective teaching and learning in the school.

Managing classroom means more than avoiding chaos in the classroom but establishing a routine that enables learning activity to proceed smoothly. According to Arikewuyo (2001) classroom management is the process of efficiently and effectively organizing the classroom for learning objectives to be achieved. This is in line with Jones and Jones (2012) who perceives classroom management as the use of rules and procedures to maintain order for quality learning to occur.

Effective classroom management is an essential precursor to creating an enabling environment for proper teaching and learning. Empirical and related studies by Akinseinde (2008), Badmus (2001) and Mayer (2002) revealed that classroom management problem encountered by teachers ranged from poor classroom discipline, poor relationship between the students and teachers, ineffective class coordination and control to dearth of leadership and poor communication. To manage these problems teachers need to possess relevant skills in classroom management.

Researchers such as Mater (2002) and Hammerness (2003), observed that many teachers reportedly lack adequate skill to effectively manage the classroom and are inconsistent in their enforcement of classroom disciplinary codes among students. A situation which reportedly creates a poor atmosphere among students. This situation appears to create a negative impact on effective classroom management and achievement of quality education. In order to effectively manage the classroom, Osakwe (2014), proffered that teachers need to adequate skill in class control. Class control has to do with teacher's ability in arranging the classroom and managing the facilities provided for students' usage. It deals with teacher's ability in keeping the students organized, focused, attentive and academically productive during the class in order to achieve classroom objectives and on the overall achieve quality education.

The concern for quality education has been at the core of the motivating forces for reforms in education, secondary schools (public and private) not left out. According to Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013), and Federal Ministry of Education (2010), the main policy objective in education in Nigeria is to raise the quality of education at all levels in order to make the recipients of the system more useful to themselves and the society as well. FME (2010) further stresses that quality teaching and learning in Nigeria education system, most especially in secondary schools, is a goal to which learners, teachers, staff and school administration should aspire to attain. These goals will not be significantly achieved if the classroom teachers fail in their responsibility.

In recent times, the urge is about issue of classroom management has become crucial, ubiquitous, and recurring in educational discourse due to the linkages of a well-managed classroom with quality learning. Effective teaching and learning can hardly be noticed in a poorly managed classroom. A well-managed classroom requires a teacher who is characterized by high knowledge of content, context, pedagogy and personal discipline (Clark & Walsh, 2002). Ogunnu (2000) opines that the success of classroom management

effectiveness is dependent on teacher's personal attributes evident in his or her standard of impeccable ethical and social conduct.

Despite all efforts to provide quality education, the secondary school system in Anambra state appears to still face challenges that could compromise the quality of education provided. Majority of the teachers in secondary school system in Anambra State seem not to possess relevant skills in classroom management that are needed to enhance students learning in order to improve the quality of education being offered to students. This appears to be why Nwanna (2012) noted that secondary schools are not living up to expectation in discharging its obligations. Ajayi (2010) also lamented that secondary education in Nigeria is riddled with crises of various dimensions and magnitude such as overcrowding and indiscipline among students in the classrooms.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria, the education system seems to be a tasteless scenario and experience. Parents and students often complain about the classroom activities of the teachers in secondary schools. Teachers on the other hand complain of students' inattentiveness, disruptive behaviour and lack of cooperation among others. This seemed to be the case in Anambra state. Teachers often complain that one of the challenges they face in carrying out their duties as teachers is how to manage their demanding classes that are most times over populated and lack sufficient learning and teaching aids which are all obstacles to effective classroom instruction for quality teaching and learning.

Teachers whose most essential activity in a typical school environment is to organize classroom activities and manage students' unacceptable behaviors seem not to have the requisite skills in taking care of these classroom activities. They also seem to lack the basic skills required to manage different classroom situations and are inconsistent in their enforcement of classroom discipline among students. The effect of this is that the students are constantly sent out of the classrooms, punished, suspended and sometimes expelled from school. This situation is worrisome and appears to hamper the achievement of quality education in schools. This study, therefore, determined the classroom management skills possessed by teachers for quality teaching and learning in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question

What are the classroom control skills adopted by teachers for enhancing quality Teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra state?

Hypotheses

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the classroom control skills they adopt for enhancing quality teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra state.

Method

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study which was carried out in public secondary schools in Anambra State. One research questions guided the study and one hypothesis was tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study was 6,350 teachers 257 public secondary schools in the State. A sample size of 672 teachers was drawn using multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected using a questionnaire of six items developed by the researchers and titled "Teachers' Class Control Skills Questionnaire" (TCCSQ). The questionnaire was validated by three experts who are lecturers from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Reliability indices obtained was 0.79. The direct administration and retrieval method was used for data collection. Mean was used to answer the research question while t-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. In analysing the data, mean ratings of 2.50 and above was regarded as agree while mean ratings of less than 2.50 was regarded as disagree. For the null hypotheses, a null hypothesis was rejected if the calculated t-value is equal or greater than the critical value while when the calculated t-value is less than the critical value, the null hypotheses was not rejected.

Results

Table 1: Mean Ratings on the Classroom Control Skills Possessed by Teachers for Enhancing Quality Teaching and Learning

	Mean	SD	Remark
1. Arrange students in rows to facilitate task behaviour and academic learning.	3.74	.44	Agree
2. Organize visual and audio aids in the classroom to facilitate learning.	2.11	.68	Disagree
3. Strategically place students with special needs or behaviour problems in the front roll.	3.46	.50	Agree
4. Ensure that the classroom is neat and tidy to enhance cleanliness	2.89	.86	Agree
5. Ensure that all seats and desks are well arranged in good order	3.38	.49	Agree
6. Display the major classroom rules and procedures agreed upon by teacher and students.	2.20	.98	Disagree

Table 1 shows that the respondents agree to four (item 31, 33, 34, and 35) of the six listed items as the classroom control skills possessed by teachers for quality teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra state. Their mean ratings for the four items ranged from 2.89 to 3.74. They however, disagree on the remaining two items (item 32 and 36) with mean 2.11 and 2.20 as part of the skills. The range of the standard deviation which fell within .44 and .98 indicates that the respondents were homogeneous in their mean ratings of the classroom control skills possessed by teachers for enhancing quality teaching and learning.

Table 2: t-test Comparison of Male and Female Teachers' Mean Ratings on Classroom Control Skills for Enhancing Quality Teaching and Learning

Source of variation	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Male	99	2.99	.26	660	1.14	.25	Not-Sig
Female	563	2.96	.27				

The result in table 2 shows that the mean score for male teachers ($M=2.99$, $SD=.26$) was not significantly greater than that of the female teachers ($M=2.96$, $SD=.27$); $t(660) 1.14$, $p=.25$. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups on their classroom control skills for enhancing quality teaching and learning was therefore not rejected.

Discussion

Teachers regard class control as a problem which they have to endure every day. In many cases teaching and learning have become difficult in some schools, and impossible in others, because some teachers appear not to understand how to foster discipline in classrooms in order to achieve quality education. Having this in perspective, the finding of this study shows that teachers agree they adopt four of the six classroom control skills listed for quality teaching and learning. These skills are: arranging students in rows to facilitate task behaviour and academic learning, strategically placing students with special needs or behaviour problems in the front roll, ensure that the classroom is neat and tidy to enhance cleanliness and ensure that all seats and desks

are well arranged in good order. This finding is in line with Ofoyuru and Too-Okema (2011), who found that class control skills such as use of light punishment, communication and counselling are used in managing students in the classroom. This also agrees with Karanja and Bowen (2012) who found in their study that school management adopt counselling and maintenance as a means of helping students move away from indiscipline in the classroom, thereby enhancing class control.

The findings of this study do not support Simatwa (2012) who in his study found that some of the methods used in maintaining class control include: canning, kneeling, slapping, pinching and smacking. Other alternatives like guidance and counselling and reprimanding were also adopted in managing students in the class according to his study. Teachers however, should always apply positive class control skills such as the ones found in this study. This will help create a conducive atmosphere and help students focus on classroom activities.

The findings of the hypothesis shows that no significant difference was found between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the classroom control skills they possess for quality teaching and learning. The reason for this appears to be because male and female teachers seem to possess the same level of class control skills.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study presented, analyzed and discussed, it was concluded that teachers possess class control skills such as arranging students in rows to facilitate task behaviour and academic learning, strategically placing students with special needs or behaviour problems in the front roll, ensure that the classroom is neat and tidy to enhance cleanliness and ensure that all seats and desks are well arranged in good order for the enhancement of quality teaching and learning in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. In order to achieve desired level of quality education, training and retraining of teaching staff should be the watchword. Workshops should be organised by the State government regularly to refresh teachers' instructional monitoring and class control skills from time to time. This will help improve teachers' skills in areas they are deficient.

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